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NATIONAL AUTHORIZATION OF PRIVATE LAUNCHING ACTIVITIES: CRITICAL COMPONENTS OF A COMMERCIAL LAUNCH LICENSE FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

With the increase in private and government-contracted space activities, licensing is a reliable way for countries to manage authorization and continuing supervision of non-governmental actors by standardizing their compliance with international obligations while encouraging innovation in the private sector by setting expectations for engineering design, approval timelines, and procurement of capital. Emerging spacefaring countries, also under obligations to authorize their private actors, should create mechanisms to authorize their nation's non-governmental entities as multi-national launching activities become more common among the private space industry.

This article discusses how nations authorize commercial space activities through regulatory licensing. States are expected to uphold international obligations set forth by the space treaties as applied to their non-governmental actors. Authorization for non-governmental space activities can be accomplished through prohibiting them, authorizing them on a case-by-case basis, and creating standards through a licensing procedure.

Using the United States' regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations as a model, together with principles derived from international space law, this report will set forth five critical components for a launch license framework to ensure international compliance and national security. Licenses must (1) be required for any private actor's launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State; (2) mandate some form of technical requirements for the launch; (3) provide a mechanism for managing financial responsibility; (4) allow for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances; and (5) be terminable by the government.

The article will also examine the United States' FAA Vehicle Operator License and the current issues in licensing space activities. Lastly, the article will discuss the path for authorizing private space activities and encouraging economic growth for emerging spacefaring countries.

KEYWORDS: Commercial launch license, Mission Authorization, Liability Convention, Emerging spacefaring nations, Space launch insurance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As private space activities become more common, licensing has become a feasible way to manage authorization and continuing supervision of non-governmental actors by standardizing a country's approach to international obligations while still encouraging innovation in the private sector. Although licensing has many benefits for streamlining government operations and managing industry players, not all spacefaring countries have regulatory launch licensing procedures. Additionally, emerging spacefaring countries, which are also under the obligation to authorize their private actors, must create mechanisms and paths to authorize their nation's non-governmental entities as private space activities become more common and increasingly international.

This article will discuss how nations may authorize commercial space activities of non-governmental actors in accordance with international obligations set forth by the space treaties. Authorization for non-governmental space activities can be accomplished through prohibiting them, authorizing them on a case-by-case basis, and creating standards through a licensing procedure.

Using the United States' regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations as a model, together with international space law, the discussion will set forth five critical components for a launch license framework which include: (1) that the license be required for any private actor's launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State; (2) mandating some form of technical requirements for the launch; (3) providing a mechanism for managing financial responsibility; (4) allowing for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances; and (5) termination of the licensed activity at any point. These five critical components for a launch license framework ensure international compliance and national security.

Lastly, the article will establish a path for authorizing private space activities and encouraging economic growth for emerging spacefaring countries.

2. INTERNATIONAL OBLIGATIONS

For commercial launch licensing and more generally any space activity, multilateral treaties provide the backdrop of international obligations for countries to then implement in their nation's launch regulations. State Parties must operate under the obligations of these treaties and uphold their values according to international law.

2.1. *Responsibility of Authorization and Continuing Supervision*

Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty states, "States Parties to the Treaty shall bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space."² Article VI also mandates that a State is internationally responsible for "national activities in outer space"³ regardless of whether "such activities are carried on by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities."⁴ This means a government bears international responsibility for the space activities of its private actors. The article continues, "[t]he activities of non-governmental entities in outer space . . . shall require authorization and continuing supervision by the appropriate State Party to the Treaty."⁵

² Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies ("Outer Space Treaty") [Article VI], January 27, 1967, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

³ von der Dunk, Frans G. (2011). The Origins of Authorisation: Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty and International Space Law. *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program Faculty Publications*, 6, 3-28. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/spacelaw/69>.

⁴ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note 2*, art. VI.

⁵ *Ibid.*

2.2. Responsibilities Arising from the Liability Convention

Beyond a state's obligation to authorize the space activities of its private actors, governments are also liable for damages caused by the space-related activities of their private actors.⁶ The Outer Space Treaty provides the first indication of managing liability in space. Article VII states, “[e]ach State Party to the Treaty that launches or procures the launching of an object into outer space . . . and each State Party from whose territory or facility an object is launched, is internationally liable for damage . . . [caused] by such object or its component parts on the Earth, in air space or in outer space.”⁷

Later, in 1972, the Liability Convention set forth more specifications for how a country would bear international liability for damages caused by launching.⁸ In Article I, the Liability Convention defines a launching State as “a state which launches or procures the launching of a space object” or “a State from whose territory or facility a space object is launched.”⁹ This text identifies four categories:¹⁰ a State that launches a space object, a State that procures the launching of a space object, a State from whose territory a space object is launched, and a State from whose facility a space object is launched.¹¹

The Liability Convention established strict liability for damages caused by space objects and launch vehicles on the surface of the Earth or in the airspace.¹² This liability is imposed upon the launching State.¹³ When there are multiple launching States, the treaty provides for joint and several liability. The convention provides means for indemnifying and exonerating for certain situations when there are multiple launching States.¹⁴ Multiple launching States are also allowed to contractually agree on how they will share liability.¹⁵

As addressed above, Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty mandates an international obligation to authorize the activities of their private actors. Article IX goes on to address the responsibility of States to act “with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties to the Treaty.”¹⁶ This principle of “due regard” addresses States’ obligations to mitigate risk, often prior to or during an incident. Whereas Article VII, together with the Liability Convention, sets forth the specifics of how an injured State may recover the damages caused by another State’s space activities after an incident occurs. It is very important to distinguish each of these obligations to correctly identify the circumstances which trigger them and how they apply.

2.3. The Obligation to Register Space Objects

In addition to the principles of the Outer Space Treaty and the obligations of the Liability Convention, State Parties must also hold their private actors accountable for complying with *the Convention on*

⁶ Liability is one of a variety of obligations States hold regarding their private actors.

⁷ *Ibid.*, art. VII.

⁸ Larsen, P.B. (2019). Outer space: How shall the world's governments establish order among competing interests? *Washington International Law Journal*, 29(1), 27–28. <https://digitalcommons.law.uw.edu/wilj/vol29/iss1/1>.

⁹ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects (“Liability Convention”) [Article I], March 29, 1972, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

¹⁰ Lee, A.Y. (2023). The Future of the Law on the Moon. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*, 88(1), 20. <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol88/iss1/2/>.

¹¹ *Ibid.*; Liability Convention, *supra* note 9, art. I (defining a space object to “include [] component parts of a space object as well as its launch vehicle and parts thereof,” and launching to “include [] attempted launching”).

¹² Liability Convention, *supra* note 9, art. II.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Ibid.* (showing multiple launching states may decide how they would divide liability and may be absolved of paying damages if they can prove they are not the responsible party).

¹⁶ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 2, art. IX.

Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (“Registration Convention”).¹⁷ Private companies are required to share information with their governments, which should then be recorded internationally.¹⁸

Gathering the information necessary to report the object is often part of the process a government uses to approve a space activity. However, gathering the information tends to relate more towards authorizing the activity and less to reporting the object according to the Registration Convention.

The Registration Convention mandates launching State report information to the United Nations “as soon as practicable.”¹⁹ Although registering a space object gives a country internationally recognized jurisdiction over the object and any personnel onboard, it is not popular, particularly for the increasing number of “disposable” space objects, like Starlink satellites.²⁰

3. NATIONAL AUTHORIZATION FOR LAUNCHING

As established by the international space law discussed above, State Parties must adhere to the obligations set forth by the multilateral space treaties. Government operations have *de facto* mission authorization required by Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty, whereas private actors require external oversight provided by their government. To define the language of this paper: in a commercial launch, the launcher is a private, or non-governmental, entity pursuing a commercial space activity. This commercial activity could be contracted work on behalf of a government agency or a strictly private activity for business or other purposes.²¹

There are three general mechanisms a government can use to manage launch activities. First, a State may prohibit any launches by non-governmental entities. Second, a State may approve of a private launch on a case-by-case basis. Third, a State may develop a licensure system to standardize the requirements for a non-governmental entity to launch.

3.1. Authorization Through Prohibition

A key part of authorization is legislation or regulation which simply prohibits private actors from conducting or participating in space launches. By prohibiting non-governmental actors, the government maintains control over the activity. There is no question as to authorizing an activity because, by the nature of the prohibition, no activities are authorized. This prohibition is the easiest first step in creating national legislation for space activities, particularly launching.

3.2. Authorization on a Case-by-Case Basis

Approval on a case-by-case basis allows for flexibility. Instead of implementing a commercial launch license, a country may accomplish its international obligation to provide “authorization and continuing supervision” on an *ad hoc* basis. *Ad hoc* approval may be beneficial for determining the parameters of a regulatory licensing procedure. However, in the long-term, case-by-case approval creates government burden. Further, it lacks predictability and reliability, which largely benefits the private space industry.

The *ad hoc* approach, or authorizing launches on an individual basis, falls short of addressing regulatory gaps as more private actors are involved in the space industry and greater international collaboration

¹⁷ Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (“Registration Convention”), November 12, 1974, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introregistration-convention.html>.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, art. IV.

²⁰ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. [Online Index of Objects Launched into Outer Space](#).

²¹ Isnardi, C. (2020). Problems with enforcing international space law on private actors. *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law*, 58(2), 492. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5daf8b1ab45413657badbc03/t/5ed6c19ec930145149b92f2f/1742287183697/%28i%29+Isnardi+%2858-2%29.pdf>.

exposes more countries to becoming a launching State. The launching State definitions include countries who procuring a launch. What it means to “procure a launch” is not clarified in the treaty; rather, it depends on treaty interpretation according to international laws of state practice.

3.3. *Authorization by a License*

Licensing private and commercial launches is the most robust option for supporting economic development of the private space industry and appropriately authorizing activities in accordance with international obligations. A licensure for regulating launches is only necessary for private actors in their launching activities. According to Article VI, private actors require “authorization and continuing supervision.”²² This necessity is not relevant to government agencies as they already “bear international responsibility for national activities in outer space.”²³

Separately, a country may choose to lay out requirements for its government agencies in the commercial launch license regulations. Containing specifications and regulations for government agency launches may be done together with a commercial launch license, as it may be convenient for legislative or regulatory purposes; however, it is not necessary. The government is already responsible for their launch, and the government is already liable for their damages. Thus, a successful licensure would provide “authorization and continuing supervision” to a country’s private actors and hold all private actors accountable to the government for their liability by applying to private actors.

Establishing a licensure defines clear regulatory guidance for when an actor would need authorization for their activity. Without regulations which ban launching without permission from the government, a national may subject their country to becoming a launching State, by procuring a launch. A licensure would lay out the necessary situations, in which an actor must obtain a launch license anytime the country becomes a launching State due to its nation’s activities. Thus, licensing would manage the country’s liability and establish clear and predictable criteria to achieve launch authorization.

3.3.1. *Necessary Components of a Launch License*

A license provides many benefits. For industry, it creates reliability and foresight into the regulatory process to gain mission authorization. Through a licensing system, companies will know the requirements for their launch to be approved and can plan to conform to those requirements. Licensures also create a level of predictability for investor funding, a critical consideration for space start-ups.

This article proposes five critical components of a licensure to operate in accordance with international obligations set forth by the space law treaties. These components are modeled after the United States’ regulations on launch and re-entry licensing found in Title 14, Chapter III of the Code of Federal Regulations. These create a framework to ensure compliance with international law and feasible domestic regulations, mindful of national security. These aspects will not be an exhaustive list of success criteria. Rather, the components explored will provide a starting point, or bare minimum, for a successful commercial launch license.

First, the license must be required for any private actor’s launching activity which would classify the country as a launching State. Second, the license must mandate some form of technical requirements to comply with international obligations. Third, the license must provide a mechanism for the government to manage financial responsibility and liability created by private actors. Fourth, the license must allow for certain waivers in exceptional circumstances. Fifth, the government must maintain the power to terminate the licensed activity.

²² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 2, art. VI.

²³ *Ibid.*

Taken together, these components provide the bare minimum for functionality and adherence to international obligations. The specifics of each component and other aspects of a commercial launch license are determined by a country's policy choices. Further, commercial launch licensures provide regulatory guidance and predictability for the developing space economy by laying out the mandatory financial requirements and technical aspects. Thus, investors and startups can secure capital accordingly and engineers can design specifications to meet the required technical criteria.

3.3.2. *Market-based Restraints*

In addition to prohibiting unauthorized activities, either on a case-by-case basis or through a license, there is an additional form of managing space activities: these are market-based and economic restraints on the private space industry. It is crucial to remember that this is not a form of government authorization required by international law. Rather, market-based restraints create a minimum threshold for private actors to pass before even reaching government authorization. The high cost of space activities is, in and of itself, a limiter.

Insurance is one way to manage liability and risk. In some instances, it is used as a form of semi-governance.²⁴ The US Department of Transportation, particularly the Federal Aviation Administration ("FAA"), regulates specific technical and probabilistic requirements for the launches it licenses through its maximum probable loss calculation, thus imposing a financial barrier.²⁵ This financial form of governance, mostly brought about by the market of space launch insurance, works alongside the other requirements. Strictly as a form of governance, it may be more subject to economic markets. Coupled with other requirements, it could be an effective manager for liability. However, using solely insurance as a form of governance could create a "pay-to-play" dynamic, giving more leeway for recklessness to wealthier, more financially savvy licensees.

Launches must first meet international requirements, and then the licensee should also have financial responsibility. This arrangement is critical to a commercial launch license. When dealing with rockets and space objects, allowing risky behavior is highly discouraged, even if a licensee could foot the bill. A space-related launch disaster could easily expand in damage astronomically due to the types of technology used in rocketry. Further, the international treaties dissuade this type of profit motive, pay-to-play behavior, as a government must authorize space activities in accordance with the obligations of the Outer Space Treaty, as well as other space treaties, in addition to being accountable for the damages caused by their private actors. Overall, launch licenses should appropriately use insurance to manage financial responsibility as a market-based solution for the cost of liability, which the government may incur from allowing a private actor to launch.

A State Party to the space treaties would not truly fulfill its duties to authorize and provide continuing supervision if the government determines eligibility based on economic factors alone. The State party must ultimately oversee all private space activities. Further, State Parties must also ensure their private actors are operating with 'due regard' and provide 'authorization and continuing supervision' for their space activities.

²⁴ Ramirez, D., & Pinto, T. (2021). Policing the police: A roadmap to police accountability using professional liability insurance. *Rutgers University Law Review*, 73(2), 329. https://www.rutgerslawreview.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/01_Ramirez-Pinto.pdf ("Insurance companies do not have any direct control over day to day of the police departments. Just as credit ratings affect rate of borrowing, insurance companies will set premium rates to reflect risk. Liability insurance will mitigate financial losses that result from litigation, thereby enabling officers and departments to focus on community safety and development, while also reducing the burden on taxpayers.").

²⁵ 14 C.F.R § 440.

4. THE US SYSTEM FOR AUTHORIZING COMMERCIAL LAUNCHES

The FAA is the US government agency that oversees launch authorization.²⁶ The commercial launch licensure was first codified into law in the 1980s and has become the gold standard in commercial launch licensing today, with many countries using the FAA Vehicle Operator License as a model.²⁷

4.1. Licensees

A critical part of licensing is to require the license for any non-governmental actor whose activities would give rise to a State being considered a “launching State” according to the Liability Convention.²⁸ This is because the State Party is the “appropriate state” to provide authorization and continuing supervision for the private actor.

The US requires a commercial launch license for anyone who fits into the following categories: (1) one who is launching from a US territory; (2) one who is an individual US citizen²⁹ or US business³⁰, outside the US; (3) one who is organized or existing under the laws of a foreign country, where a US citizen or US business has a “controlling interest”³¹ in the one and the launch is outside the US and outside of another country’s territory;³² or (4) one in a foreign country’s territory, where there is a “controlling interest” and where it is agreed that the US has jurisdiction.³³

These categories are wide; they encompass any activity in which the US would be a launching State by covering whenever a US citizen launches or procures the launching of a space object, or launches from a US territory or facility.³⁴ A license must regulate activities which would classify the country as a launching State according to the Liability Convention. This allows a country to authorize the activity and manage the liability it creates for the national government.

4.2. Technical Requirements

International space law also requires specific practices and prohibitions in space, which apply to both governmental and non-governmental activity. Specifically, there is a requirement to register space objects, a prohibition on weapons of mass destruction, a duty to avoid harmful contamination, and the mandate to exercise ‘due regard’ as they carry out space activities.³⁵ The duty to register space objects comes from the Registration Convention. The prohibition of weapons of mass destruction comes from Article IV of the Outer Space Treaty. Article IX mandates that Parties “conduct exploration [] as to avoid [] harmful contamination” and act with ‘due regard.’ The US uses its payload review process, as well as other

²⁶ 51 U.S.C. § 50901(b)(3).

²⁷ Sundahl, M.J. (2019). Business, Legal, and Policy Issues in Relation to Increased Private Space Activity. *Law Faculty Articles and Essays*. https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/fac_articles/971.

²⁸ von der Dunk, F.G. (2011). *National space legislation in Europe: Issues of authorisation of private space activities in the light of developments in European space cooperation* (pp. 13-14). (Vol. 6). Brill, Nijhoff. <https://doi.org/10.1163/ej.9789004204867.iii-381.9>.

²⁹ US citizen, as used in the paper, will have the ordinary definition, unless otherwise specified to be the 51 USC § 50902 definition of “Citizen of the United States.”

³⁰ US business, as used in this section, means, “an entity organized or existing under the laws of the United States or a State.” See 51 U.S.C. § 50902(1)(B).

³¹ “Controlling interest means ownership of an amount of equity in such entity sufficient to direct management of the entity or to void transactions entered into by management. Ownership of at least fifty-one percent of the equity in an entity by persons described in paragraph (1) or (2) of this definition creates a rebuttable presumption that such interest is controlling.” 14 C.F.R § 401.5

³² The most significant example is a water launch in international waters. This would also apply to territories which are unclaimed by any nation, like Antarctica.

³³ As established by 51 U.S.C. § 50904.

³⁴ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*, art. I.

³⁵ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note 2*.

mechanisms in the general licensing process, to implement these technical provisions to follow the requirements under international law. In addition to ensuring missions meet international obligations, technical specifications can standardize engineering and safety requirements for launch operations. This establishes clear standards that private industry must meet in order to procure a license for their space launch.

4.3. *Financial Responsibility*

Any damage caused by a private actor to another launching State creates financial liability for the private actor's government. Because that launching State would be beholden to other countries for damages their launches cause on the ground, governments must mandate their private actors to maintain a certain level of financial responsibility.³⁶ The US manages this liability by determining the amount for which an actor is financially responsible, mandating insurance or demonstrated financial responsibility, and providing indemnification in cases where damages exceed the actor's financial responsibility.³⁷

Recalling the Liability Convention, which mandates strict liability for damages caused on the surface of the earth or aircraft in flight.³⁸ Because the liability is absolute, countries must prepare their launchers to assume financial responsibility for their activities. A successful commercial launch license will cover the liability of a country created by international law, up to an appropriate level for the respective country. There are many ways a nation can distribute financial responsibility. Furthermore, there are also policy factors to determine what level of risk is appropriate for the country's government and economic goals. The US uses a capping method to limit the liability of private actors, along with a calculation of each launch's level of risk.

To establish the amount for which a private actor may be liable, the Secretary of Transportation, together with consultation from other government agencies determine the maximum probable loss ("MPL") for the applicant's launching activity.³⁹ This "forms the basis for financial responsibility requirements" in launch licenses.⁴⁰ MPL is defined as "the greatest dollar amount of loss for bodily injury or property damage that is reasonably expected to result from a licensed or permitted activity."⁴¹

The US established that a licensee must obtain insurance or demonstrate financial responsibility up to the lesser of the MPL or "the maximum liability insurance available on the world market at reasonable cost if the amount is less than the applicable."⁴² The costs associated with damages beyond the MPL would then be indemnified by the government, up to a certain point.

The result of not mandating financial responsibility for a private actor releases that actor from the liability of their activities. This would cause a government to become completely responsible for the costs of any damage caused by a private actor, without a convenient and legal way to recover money from the private actor. Thus, mechanisms for distributing financial responsibility are necessary for a commercial launch license.

4.4. *Waiver*

For the US to maintain control over their launching activities and abide by its own legislation, the regulations must provide for authorizing a launch outside of the licensing procedure in exceptional circumstances. The Secretary of Transportation may waive a requirement or the license if "the waiver is

³⁶ Liability Convention, *supra note* 9.

³⁷ 51 U.S.C. §§ 50914-15.

³⁸ Liability Convention, *supra note* 9, art. II.

³⁹ 14 C.F.R. § 440.7(b) (2023).

⁴⁰ 14 C.F.R. § 440.7(a) (2023).

⁴¹ 14 C.F.R. § 440.3 (2023).

⁴² 51 U.S.C. § 50914(a)(3).

in the public interest and will not jeopardize the public health and safety, safety of property, and national security and foreign policy interests of the United States.”⁴³ Further, the law prohibits waiver if a human is on board the launch.⁴⁴ This statutory language outlines who may waive requirements for a license, factors to consider, and any exceptions to waiving.⁴⁵ This protects the sovereignty of a nation’s launching activities and allows for a legal option for private and commercial actors to launch without a license if it is in the best interest of the nation. Ultimately, the government is responsible for any liability that results from the launching activity.⁴⁶ So, deviations to the license procedure take on more risk and should be exceptional in nature.

4.5. Termination

The regulations should also allow for suspension or termination in appropriate circumstances. This allows a country’s government to have necessary and ultimate control over launching. The US license allows for the prohibition, suspension, or immediate termination of a licensed launch “if the Secretary decides the launch or operation or reentry is detrimental to the public health and safety, the safety of property, or a national security or foreign policy interest of the United States.”⁴⁷ These considerations are open-ended, which allows the US to maintain control legally over its private actors.

Termination, like waiver, legally gives a State necessary control over its private actors’ launching activities. This control is mandatory to international obligations created in the Outer Space Treaty Article VI. Further, this control can provide for national security by terminating a launch when national security is at risk.

According to 51 U.S.C. 50908(c)(2), the Secretary of Transportation may suspend or revoke a license if it is “necessary to protect the public health and safety, the safety of property, or a national security or foreign policy interest of the United States.” Thus, “foreign policy interests”, including international obligations that the US owes according to the space treaties, are grounds for terminating the license.

For a license to adhere to the international obligations, termination is a critical component to maintain control. The State should be able to terminate authorization of space activity if there is a failure or risk of failure in adhering to international obligations.

5. CONSIDERATIONS FOR EMERGING SPACEFARING COUNTRIES

For an emerging spacefaring country, the first steps to authorizing national space activity would be through prohibiting its own private actors from unapproved launches. Next, there should be a way to obtain permission to launch or be a part of procuring a launch activity. This would mean designating a particular governmental body to contact. A later step is to create a licensing procedure if this makes sense for the nation’s private and commercial space economy. A license can provide many benefits to the private sector, including predictability and reliability.

Another consideration is how modern space activities are more complex and do not fit neatly into one category. As international collaboration increases across the globe, the division between how multiple parties procure a launch begins to blur. Consider the variety of components, intellectual property, and manufacturing that go into a single launch vehicle.

Today, there is a deep understanding of how space activities are more complex and require multiple types of licensures and approvals. The US and its commercial launch license now face issues in trying to keep pace with the private industry’s demands. The regulatory burden of the commercial launch license can be

⁴³ 51 U.S.C. § 50905(b)(3).

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ Liability Convention, *supra note 9*, art. II.

⁴⁷ 51 U.S.C. § 50909(a).

felt by large space companies, like SpaceX, and small start-ups, like Varda Space Industries. The regulatory scheme has become cumbersome.

The US had built a system where different federal agencies manage different activities according to their delegated authority on Earth. For example, among the FAA, the Office of Space Commerce, and the Federal Communications Commission (“FCC”), each has a speciality in authorizing launching and reentry, remote sensing, and spectrum management. However, the strict separation of their authority to license space activities has proven to be an incredible regulatory burden. Further, “novel” space activities do not fit into any of the US’s established licensing systems.

These issues give rise to the call for a one-stop-shop system, where one government entity is responsible for the entire licensing of space activity. Rather than multiple agencies managing different aspects of the same space mission, one agency would provide convenience, clarity, and greater speed for navigating a complex licensing process.⁴⁸ A one-stop shop for licensing space activities is a large hope for the commercial space industry. However, the US seems too far into its current structure to truly implement a singular agency approach.

The space industry and the history of US commercial space show that a singular agency design would be the most effective and flexible for modern and novel space activities. Countries that are now looking to create a licensure for commercial activities should deeply consider how they wish to divide operations and responsibilities in licensing space activities, if at all.

Beyond a “one-stop-shop” structure, countries must also consider the economic implications of their licensing. While licensing is an important step for encouraging a country’s private space industry, it also draws resources away from other operations of the government. In addition to structural considerations for designing national legislation to authorize space activities, countries should also look to their private industry needs and trends. What sort of activity is common and requires more governmental support? What other countries do businesses tend to partner with for space operations? Economic and political factors will also play a role in dedicating resources to encouraging space activities nationally. A cost-benefit analysis may assist in determining the appropriate dedication to licensing operations compared with the economic benefit caused by private space activity.

As more countries expand their space operations and encourage growth for their private space companies, the need for licensure systems grows. Further research can illuminate more aspects of law, policy, and economics as scholars continue to inspect commercial launching through the lens of various countries and their economies. This would benefit countries, especially emerging spacefaring countries, as they explore and determine policy choices for their own commercial launch licensure.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has applied the international obligations of the space treaties to create a framework for authorizing national activities, particularly non-governmental launching activities. The need for responsible commercial launch licensing is growing, demonstrating a need for countries to adopt a licensure system which will: regulate the actors whose activities would give the country status as a launching State, determine technical specifications, provide mechanisms to distribute financial liability, and include possible waiver and termination of the license. Through implementing these components, a country will create a functional commercial launch licensing system that respects both its obligations under international space law and its sovereignty and security in managing its private actors.

⁴⁸ Clayson, Z., Spellman, F., Patel, S., & Shen, D. (2023, August 8). *Space mission authorization: Enabling the final frontier*. War on the Rocks. <https://warontherocks.com/2023/08/space-mission-authorization-enabling-the-final-frontier>

As countries with a long history of space missions and regulatory experience, like the US, analyze and reconstruct their launch licensing procedures, emerging spacefaring countries can find guidance from their experience and history, as well as the issues that face their government systems and industry today. On the path to full participation in space, the language of the Outer Space Treaty obliges countries to promote peace and benefit for each other: a truly unifying mission for the advancement of all humankind. Authorizing national activities for commercial launching is a first and fundamental step to supporting and bolstering space policy around the globe as humanity shoots for the stars.